

Challenges of Cultural Divergences for Transnational Organizations

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Abstract

This article aims at exploring the challenges that cross-cultural divergences engender for communication within multinational organizations. Global organizations do, in fact, tend to share multicultural values. However, in order to prevent misunderstanding and conflicting attitudes, the attendants' cultural dissimilarities must be managed quite delicately. The implications of such challenges will be explored by evaluating conflicts between national identities and global values, investigating the intricate nature of transnational coalitions, examining the importance of multicultural intelligence for organizational relationships, and analyzing the potential disruptions of cultural divergences. Consequently, in order to lessen the difficulties that their cultural differences may produce, the members of transcultural organizations ought to prevent cultural clashes and foster intercultural harmony.

Keywords: challenges, intercultural divergences, transnational organizations.

1. Introduction

The globalization process is primarily driven by technology and economic factors, but intercultural characteristics also need to be greatly improved. These aspects make up the main mechanisms of communication among participants in international organizations. Therefore, in order to prevent communication breakdowns that could impair their ability to function, cross-cultural harmony is required of the attendees. Incorporating cultural factors within the globalization framework is essential in order to establish efficient international communication

channels. Globally, organizational culture is evolving into a comprehensive collection of widely accepted beliefs, customs, and standards. Such notions allow these organizations to guarantee the agreement of their members, which has a significant effect on their intercommunication process. Furthermore, in global perceptions, cultural diversity constitutes a constructive action for the enrichment of communication within transnational workspaces, particularly when the partakers have reached the required degree of collaboration. Explicitly, it is important to inquire about managers' awareness of the risks associated with cultural differences in transcultural organizations. Based on the study, two research questions emerge from the examination: what cultural obstacles do these organizations encounter, and how can they overcome them? Accordingly, in line with the research problem, the objectives of this study are to analyze the challenges brought about by the participants' cultural differences and the strategies that may be used to foster greater cross-cultural agreement in order to mitigate those challenges.

2. Transcultural Standards and Cultural Divergences

Transcultural values are steadily disturbed by the combination of cultural individualities, conflicting hopes and discrimination threats. This combination reveals that, in spite of the challenges of transnational relationships, multiculturalists can cultivate appropriate mechanisms of intercultural communication. To enhance dealings associated with such mechanisms, social multiplicity within these relationships should be established through multicultural awareness. This awareness would generate smooth interaction of cross-cultural openness. As cited by Hall and Theriot (2016), Trompenaars and Hampden-Turner hold that “the cultural awareness and skills that make people culturally competent are lacking today, in a time when these qualities are most needed. Without cultural awareness and skills, operational gridlock can occur at great cost to the workplace” (p. 35). Explicitly, coordination needs of transnational contacts have led to a significant removal of local cultural barriers, which transferred the international cultural landscape from individual identities to globalized values. Similarly, the information and communication technologies that support globalization of culture are perceived as a drive toward the establishment of a universal experience worldwide. In this respect, Mazur (2010) points out in his description of the intrinsic change made by globalization for peoples' interconnections that “increasing globalization requires more interaction among people from diverse cultures, beliefs, and backgrounds than ever before. People no longer live and work in an insular marketplace” (p. 5). In other words, given the

global context, multicultural competence is crucial for increasing people's capacity to overcome obstacles produced by hostile reactions that arise from cultural distinctiveness.

Indeed, people that attend multinational organizations have to put aside their individual egocentrism and engage in collaborative connections instead. In these connections, what matters most is the synthesis of values and perspectives that results from cultural diversity. Thus, individuals who have been exposed to a global context learn that all cultures must be respected. This idea is well demonstrated by Moran et al. (2011) who argue that

A global person does not believe that his/her nation is the best at everything and that everyone else wants to be just like him/her-rather he/she is aware that other cultures of the world have lives and viewpoints different from his/her own (p. 9).

Clearly then, globalists should believe in universal principles and be impregnated with full respect for the different cultural identities all over the world. This conviction would help them recognize that other cultures have their own lifestyles and perspectives. Likewise, cross-cultural communication has been fueled by globalized systems that have begun to apply universal cultural techniques that are suggested for handling transnational frameworks. The fundamental foundation of these systems is the equality of all people worldwide. In this regard, Einstein, cited by Moran et al. (2011), holds that “all people are to some extent like some other people. This is the cultural aspect which we share, in part, with people from our own tribe” (p. 10). That is, to create global multiculturalism persevere, cross-cultural policymakers should build their approaches as to boost minded-openness and encourage cultural flexibility and tolerance.

In short, multicultural competences are necessary in global environments to help their members overcome barriers brought on by negative responses to their cultural differences. Successful globalists ought to recognize transnational values and be fully respectful of the diverse cultural identities that make up the global cultural landscape. Therefore, to maintain cross-cultural harmony, global organizations need to develop their strategies based on promoting cultural tolerance, anthropological flexibility, and open-mindedness.

3. Global Values and Cross-cultural Adaptability

Nations and cultures have been intricately interwoven during the past few decades. This change seems to be reshaping the values that underpin human interactions in favor of a transnational communication process infused with universal values. Thus, the structural basis of

communication is the extent to which individuals with diverse cultural backgrounds may engage in joint interaction without experiencing conflict. This engagement necessitates their readiness to set aside their innate sensitivities in order to benefit from unbiased communication. Nonetheless, even if people in multicultural environments decide to embrace a shared communication style, they usually are not able to surpass their sociocultural oddities. Consequently, maintaining a constant awareness of the norms associated with the process of globalization is essential for the suitable management of intercultural communication efforts. For intercultural understanding, the modes of communication between people and communities should be adjusted to the appreciation of their respective cultural backgrounds. This view is well demonstrated by Watson (2017) who contends that “a rudimentary version of world culture is taking shape among certain individuals who share similar values, aspirations, or lifestyles. The result is a collection of elite groups whose unifying ideals transcend geographical limitations” (p. 1). It transpires that the global cultural landscape has bewilderedly expanded and has been molded by people with divergent cultural origins who are committed to global cultural values. In such situations, intercultural subtleties should be taken into consideration to ensure an effective cross-functional processing of the international organizations’ attendants, which would help them reach their common objectives.

In the same vein, to promote successful cross-border communication, cultural differences need to be managed very carefully, which would help avoid obstacles that could obstruct cooperative partnerships. That is, any frustration feelings that may result from intercultural disagreement within the organization would generate clashes susceptible to disrupt the members’ coherence. This idea is well articulated by Thomas et al., cited by Adler and Aycan (2018) “culturally intelligent individuals switch between cultural frameworks or systems in response to environmental demands” (p. 311). Clearly then, culturally competent people can transition between different cultural frameworks and systems based on multicultural principles. Such capability makes interaction between individuals of divergent cultural backgrounds governed by universal standards, which entails that management of cultural differences draws its principles from understanding the globalized ethics. However, the complexity of the international cultural landscape is likely to generate potential challenges for global organizations. Such challenges could hinder effective interactions between contributors who expect to enhance the output of these organizations. Therefore, globalist managers need to build adequate platforms able to facilitate communication between cultures worldwide. To foster

trust and faith in the communal mission among the different participants, such communication must be predicated on mutual respect of their own cultural values.

Briefly, the intermingling of diverse cultures in global organizations, combined with the limitations imposed by cultural divergences, often hinders the partakers' collaboration, which is crucial for maintaining their interactive entente. This bewilderedness requires a common determination of these organizations to foster intercultural rapprochement and inclusiveness of their members, which would help them transcend cultural constraints.

4. Cultural Challenges for Transnational Organizations

Participants in global organizations need to interact faithfully with one another. Such an interaction presupposes intercultural reverence and social agreement. Therefore, these participants must be ready to encourage and undertake multifaceted missions pertaining to the management of international organizations. Cross-national teams that take part to international associations should be aware of the potential challenges brought on by cultural dissimilarities. Such dissimilarities can create clans based on cultural belongingness, which could lead to the breakdown of these associations. In this respect, Hussain (2018) argues that "in a multicultural organization, it is only through the effective communication that the information is shared, trust is built, and constructive relation is developed and maintained. Organizational communication is as broad in its domain as the field of communication itself" (p. 45). It could be gleaned from the quote that positive relationships and mutual trust are established via an inclusive entrepreneurship that cause effective union of the organization's members. So, preparedness for global meetings has to be based on the ability to correctly interpret the participants' cultural characteristics and to develop cross-cultural communication techniques. Another dimension of cultural challenges faced by global assemblies is building friendly relations with the different attendees whose misunderstanding may lead to failure. For this purpose, coaching programs should be applied to manage the complexity of intercultural contexts. Furthermore, practical mechanisms, such as linguistic and communication styles uniformity, are to be operationalized with full respect of cultural individualities so as to mitigate cultural clashes.

By the same token, common sense and universal values are to be incorporated into the member's daily actions. This incorporation would help reach the needed interoperability amid the organizations' members and pave the way for enhancing their productivity. In order to improve collective production, cross-cultural competences would allow these members to developing skills that ensure effective interaction in their activities within the organization. According to

Raewf and Thabit, cited by Raewf and Mahmood (2021) state in their analysis of management of cultural diversity in the workplace “cultural abilities are strengthened to build a capacity to recognize and communicate with people through communities and to work efficiently together with them on dysfunctional cultural values and calendars” (p. 3). Along with this quote, it could be assumed that multicultural competences would foster in the community of an organization the ability to identify strategies that support prioritizing cooperative performances founded on universal principles. Working together, the groups engaged can more easily integrate into the organization's common values. As a result, even if cross-cultural settings are not easy to manage, a communal willingness of rapprochement from the different members could give birth to successful multicultural interactions. In this regard, Constantin et al. (2015) see that cultural consciousness turns out to be vital essentially “when we have to interact with people from other cultures. Individuals should be aware that it is difficult to think and behave in the context of their own culture within the confines of another culture” (p. 3). Therefore, the institution of a global communication system is likely to improve intercultural harmony within the transnational organizations, as it engenders awareness among the different attendants. In addition, linguistic approaches, such as verbal interpretation and transcultural orientation courses, could be operational in ensuring clarity of communication, which is vital to the overall success of cultural rapprochement.

Subsequently, international conferences focusing on interactions between different countries require thorough communication among the attendees. These interactions rely on the presence of suitable uniformity and mutual understanding. As a result, such uniformity would encourage cross-cultural rapprochement and support the activities that the organizations' members undertake based on common values. Therefore, multicultural intelligence is to be skillfully exploited to help the organization's participants bypass all threats of cultural disagreements.

5. Multicultural Intelligence for Fostering Organizational Communication

One enduring aspect of communication in multicultural workplaces is the exchange of opinions among individuals from different countries. These people gain self-satisfaction from their shared understanding with other organization members. To provide collective input, it is necessary to take into account the individual viewpoints of each participant. Therefore, an organization participants must skillfully address cultural sensitivities in order to prevent misunderstanding in their intercommunications. According to Stefanovska and Tanushevski (2016)

The organizational culture is a complex set of ideologies, norms of behavior, attitudes, opinions, symbols and core values shared throughout the organization, affecting the way the organization meets its objectives, and certainly helping the regulation and control of employee conduct (p.2).

It could be inferred from the quote that organizational culture is the intricate web of common beliefs, behaviors, and basic values that consolidates a transnational organization. It has an impact on how the organization accomplishes its objectives and is essential for managing their members' conduct. Every level of an organization management is based on how its members' views interact, especially with regard to the way they perceive collective contacts. As cited by Keyton (2017), McPhee and Zaig observe that “communication is also tailored to interrelated and overlapping organizational functions” (p. 3). Clearly then, in order to maintain a rational communication process within an organization, all partners must be able to keep a careful balance between their own perspectives and those held by their associates.

Correspondingly, management frameworks within multicultural organizations must account for the collaborative dynamics among individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. For managers of such organizations, fostering effective communication stands as a paramount objective, achievable through investing the cultural diversity of their fellows. As cited by Chhetry (2020), Adler and Gundersen argue that “every leader and employee working in the organizations which are globally operated requires multicultural skills. It is because, in the multinational companies, multiculturalism has huge effects” (p. 4). Subsequently, it seems logical that multicultural forums need to be designed so as to cultivate tolerance and broadmindedness among partakers with divergent cultural identities. Orientation programs that aim for a greater level of intercultural consciousness could help reach this level. Such a procedure would decrease misunderstanding incidents and assist the organization attendants in exploiting cultural diversity to foster productivity inside the workspace. Moreover, in order to actively participate in a multinational organization, it is necessary to support true intercultural sympathy, regardless of people's initial attitudes about cultural distinctions. As such, the lens that is used to evaluate cultural variety must be adjusted in order to align with shared norms and perspectives.

Thus, intercultural communication within transnational organizations is intrinsically based on the sharing of perspectives among their different members. These members must go beyond their cultural divergences to promote intercultural rapprochement. Yet, this accomplishment

requires a skillful handling of cross-cultural conflicts that may pose some challenges for their intercommunication process. Such intercommunication calls for creative strategies meant to enhance the sense of solidarity between the participants.

6. Dynamizing Multiculturalism of Global Contexts

A type of cultural hegemony is created by the dynamic process of the global cultural system, which could result in future clashes with national identities. Therefore, in order to ascertain the true interconnection between intercultural indicators and the behaviors of cultural communities, it is essential to measure them from multiple angles. Therefore, the social mechanisms relevant to this process should be depicted with an aim of advancing objectives that help accomplish a balance between the regional and global facets of cultural identities. Increasing intercultural contact would lead to the evolution of a shared cultural framework and the eventual transformation of the global organizations into multicultural platforms. In their study of the relationship between transnational dealings and cultural competences, Remhof et al. (2013) note that “international exposure influences the intention to work abroad through the development of cultural intelligence, which in turn positively affects the intention” (p. 226). Stated differently, universal standards are foreseeable to help integrate people and communities with diverse cultural backgrounds. People throughout the world will be connected by this agreement, which is expected to lessen interpersonal problems. Therefore, bias and personal preference should be eliminated from international settings. The people involved would then look for avoiding cross-cultural conflicts and fostering harmony within their organization. This dynamic is expected to help remove prejudiced attitudes and personal inclination for particular national cultures. Such accomplishments undoubtedly enable these people to embrace the organizational values and work for entire integration in the shared objectives.

Global communication entails adopting the perspective of multidimensional interdependent environment. Attendees of such a setting should therefore have the necessary level of multicultural competence to comprehend the context in which they operate and know how to adapt to its principles. This achievement mostly rests on one’s capacity to cultivate the required intercommunication skills that are fundamental for his/her cross-cultural integration. Likewise, people attending workspaces in a global environment are likely to have low morale due to unfriendliness, which would hinder their performance. Therefore, members of international teams must be ready to manage cultural differences by adjusting their mindset and behavior to fit the context in which they operate. Subtle handling of these differences is expected to create

the environment required for cross-cultural inclusiveness. According to Belhoste and Monin (2013), “people still refer to national culture, but without essentializing or negatively evaluating cultural differences. Rather, national differences call actors to adapt their attitudes and behaviors according to what they understand” (p.13). That is, in order to overpass transcultural barriers, cultural differences should be carefully controlled. Moreover, transcultural managers need to produce communication systems based on mutual respect for different cultural backgrounds. These systems will incite the attendees of a transnational organization to think of dealing with individual cultures without prejudice. Such a conviction would make it more practical for managers and followers to positively carry out the organization activities.

In brief, universal principles can facilitate the assimilation of individuals and groups from diverse cultural backgrounds. This agreement will help connect people globally, which is likely to reduce interpersonal conflicts. Intrinsicly, stereotypes would be eliminated from global cultural frameworks. Therefore, global organizations are called to set up intercommunication mechanisms that foster reciprocal esteem of national identities. Such approaches are meant to spark interest in the organization's shared goals and so accelerate intercultural reconciliation.

7. Conclusion

To sum up, attendants of transnational organizations need inevitably to engage in interactive connection with other people and groups from divergent cultural backgrounds. Global communication standards must be established in order to achieve the appropriate level of mutual understanding. Likewise, national identities should be adapted to the international communication standards. Therefore, fostering coherence and decreasing cross-cultural hostilities in global contexts require a high level of multicultural consciousness. Stated differently, intercultural communication is seen as a means of promoting fruitful relationships between individuals with disparate cultural origins. Through these relationships, the participants in transnational organizations will be able to get along more cooperative interactions based on common ideals. Such ideals are designed to enable these participants to engage in meaningful intercommunications within multicultural settings. Clearly then, multinational intelligence constitutes a strategic guarantee for mitigating disagreements among members of international organizations. Confirming positive communication between cultures within these organizations is necessary for establishing universal human values as a distinct intercommunication system.

Since globalization is an inevitable process, it represents a dominant phenomenon that can force changes to national cultural identities with regard to morality, human interaction, and lifestyle choices. Consequently, transcultural communication is increasingly being shaped by the globalization trend that is based on universal human values. This process would encourage intercultural dialogue and allow constructive interactions in globalized environments. At that point, one could argue that effective intercultural communication is meant to help creating transnational institutions such as the United Nations and its subsidiary organizations. These institutions will assist individuals globally in achieving the degree of cultural rapprochement necessary for the strengthening of universal principles. However, the degree of interconnectedness in today's globalized globe can be rather overwhelming, which may cause sensitive responses from various local cultures. This paradox leads to various challenges, most of which are associated with the cultural diversity of the participants in international institutions. In order to overcome these challenges, the participants must have effective transcultural consciousness, which enables them to make an adequate balance between the local and global aspects of a transnational organization. This kind of accomplishment enables the organization to effectively address different challenges arising from cross-cultural discrepancies.

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